

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 653605”

Innovative Climate-Control System to Extend Range of Electric Vehicles and Improve Comfort (XERIC)

H2020 - GV - 2014 / GV - 2 - 2014 (RIA)

RIA n° 653605

Start Date: 1st June 2015 - Duration: 36 months

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Report:

XERIC’s 4th Newsletter

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Summary:

This is the fourth of XERIC’s e-newsletters. The e-newsletters are released twice a year.

This deliverable explains how the e-newsletters are created and sent and who the subscribers are.

The newsletter is then displayed. The newsletter reaches more than 50 institutions, among which 19 industries and 14 academic organisations.

The appendices display the full versions of the editorial and the 2 interviews introduced in the newsletter.

Document history and validation

When	Who	Type	Comments
12.05.2017	Mathilde BOUCHER (EMH)	Preparation version 1 (V1)	

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1. Creating and sending e-newsletters

The e-newsletters are created thanks to the *WordPress* Content Management System.

The e-newsletters are sent automatically **as emails**. The software splits the mailing list in several sub-lists so that the e-newsletter is not considered as a spam.

The receivers can either view the e-newsletter directly in the message body or open a page in their browser.

2. Subscribers

Mailing lists were created in 2015 for the different communication purposes that we may have for the XERIC project. The starting point was each of the XERIC partners and their own professional mailing lists. There were 123 subscribers in 2015. The total number of subscribers rose to 150 in May 2016, then to 268 since December 2016.

XERIC's fourth newsletter was sent to all 268 subscribers.

People can unsubscribe thanks to an “unsubscribe” button at the bottom of the e-newsletter.

3. Newsletter 4

Please click [here](#) to read XERIC's 4th newsletter online.

Screenprints of the newsletter are displayed on the next pages.

See appendices for all the links to pdf documents that can be opened when browsing the newsletter online.

Display problems ? View this newsletter in your browser.

Newsletter 4 - May 2017

Editorial by Project Coordinator

We are about to start the third and final year of our project. We had our 5th project meeting last month in Monaco. At this time we were glad to assess that the project is well on track and partners are determined to use the final year of the project to reach our anticipated objective ! (...)

The three-fluids combined membrane contactor (3F-CMC) prototype is expected to be ready by mid-Summer and soon afterwards the small-scale prototype of the entire climate control system will be prepared and tested.(...)

We had our second XERIC's workshop in the framework the EVER Monaco 2017 Conference (from 11 to 13 April 2017). (...) I am glad to report that one of the papers presented by XERIC members has received the special award as "Best paper on ecological vehicles"!

And **Save The Date**: a new get-together is already in sight. XERIC will organize its third workshop in the framework of the third edition of the Genoa Smart Week "the power of innovation", which is going to take place in **Genoa, IT on November 20-24, 2017**.

Nino Gaeta - GVS spa - XERIC's Coordinator

[Read full editorial](#)

Get to know the XERIC team members - INTERVIEWS

Irene ESLAVA

AIN Tech, Spain

Irene Islava is an engineer and project manager at AIN, specialized in environmental projects. She is carrying out a Life Cycle Assessment to better know and address the environmental impact associated with the new XERIC climate control system. Quite a challenge !

"I find it motivating to carry out a life cycle assessment of new systems and components not modeled to date."

[Read the full interview](#)

Clemens ALEXOWSKY

UDE, Germany

Clemens Alexowsky is doing its PhD at the University of Duisburg-Essen. As a part of the XERIC project his research is about preparation and characterization of membranes.

For him "the biggest challenge is to combine all parts to one working unit, as the project will only be successful if every single part reaches its goal".

[Read the full interview](#)

Discover XERIC partners' expertise

AIN

The Asociación de la Industria Navarra is a private non-profit organization owned by its member companies (around 120) that finances itself by providing specialized services in different areas of knowledge and key

specialties to the management and development of companies and organizations.

The Engineering business unit actively supports companies that comply with sustainable development guidelines and respect the environment, not only fulfilling legal requirements, but also applying the most adequate available technologies.

[Read more](#)

BIG SUCCESS for XERIC at EVER Monaco 2017 !

Xeric organized its 2nd workshop in the frame of the **EVER Monaco Forum**, from 11 to 13 April 2017, through the **Special Lecture Session on New Progress in Air Conditioning and Thermal Management Systems for Electric Vehicles**. More than one hundred academic and industrial representatives of 27 different nationalities attended to the EVER scientific conferences this year.

A XERIC's exhibition stand has also been set up and Nino Gaeta, as XERIC's coordinator, presented the project in a roundtable organized during the first day.

XERIC's consortium has received two awards : the "Best Special Session" and the "Best paper on ecological vehicles" !

[Read more \(with links to upload the scientific papers presented\)](#)

SAVE THE DATE: 3d workshop of the project in Genoa on November 20-24, 2017

The power of innovation

Genova Smart Week - III edition
Autumn 2017

The city of Genoa will host this autumn the third edition of the "Genova Smart Week": a week of conferences, technical and educational workshops, expo and networking events that will be attended by national and international players to share their views

about innovations for the development of a livable city.

The ideal place to organize the 3d workshop of XERIC ! Let's stay in touch : you will soon get more information about it.

[Click here to read more about XERIC](#)

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[Unsubscribe](#)

4. Appendices

- Editorial by Nino Gaeta, XERIC's coordinator;
- 2 interviews (Irene Eslava – AIN ; Clemens Alexowsky – UDE);

XERIC's partners determined to reach the anticipated objective !

Welcome to our fourth newsletter.

We are about to start the third and final year of our project. It involves eight partners and one associate partner which are ambitiously working **to develop an energy-friendly climate-control system for electric vehicles** capable to reduce by more than 50% the energy used for passenger comfort all over the year.

We had our 5th project meeting last month in Monaco. At this time we were glad to assess that the project is well on track and partners are determined to use the final year of the project to reach our anticipated objective !

The three-fluids combined membrane contactor (3F-CMC) prototype is expected to be ready by mid-Summer and soon afterwards the small-scale prototype of the entire climate control system will be prepared and tested.

We had our second XERIC's workshop just after the 5th project meeting. It was held in Monaco **in the framework the EVER2017 Conference (from 11 to 13 April 2017)**. More than one hundred academic and industrial representatives coming from 27 different nationalities attended the conference. I am glad to report that one of the papers presented by XERIC members - the paper presented by Carlo Isetti, Enrico Nannei (Ticass), Stefano Lazzari (UNIGE), Bernardo Cerrai and Sergio Nari (Frigomar) – has received the special award as **"Best paper on ecological vehicles"**!

Save the date: a new get-together is already in sight! **XERIC will organize its third workshop** in the framework of the third edition of the Genoa Smart Week "the power of innovation", which is going to take place **in Genoa, IT on November 20-24, 2017**.

More on page 2

In this edition of our newsletter, you'll also get a glimpse into the daily working life of Irene Islava from AIN and Clemens Alexowsky From UDE, two of the XERIC's consortium members.

Finally, **we welcome any comments or suggestion from all people interested in our project** and we invite you to read more about it on our website: www.xeric.eu. We would also be glad to include in our mailing list you or people that you might think would be interested in receiving updates about XERIC events and development.

In order to be included in our mailing list please contact Mathilde at mathilde.boucher@umontpellier.fr.

Enjoy the issue !

Nino Gaeta
GVS SPA
XERIC's Coordinator

European Research & Innovation Project
Innovative climate-control system to extend range of electric vehicles and improve comfort

Interview with **Irene ISLAVA**

Engineer and project manager
at the Asociación de la Industria Navarra (AIN), Spain

Irene ISLAVA

is an engineer and project manager at AIN, specialized in environmental projects. In the frame of XERIC she is carrying out a Life Cycle Assessment (with a Life Cycle Cost Analysis) to better know and address the environmental impact associated with the new XERIC climate control system.

Can you please tell us a little bit about yourself through your career path ?

I graduated in mechanical engineering in 1995 at Public University of Navarre, in Pamplona, the city I was born and where I live. In the following two years I worked for two companies, dealing mainly with quality management, and industrial facilities projects. After this short time I joined Engineering department of AIN in 1997, where I specialized in environmental projects and studies. At AIN I have worked in different projects related to environment and energy, both as a technician and as a project manager. I am Project Manager Professional (PMP) since 2013.

What does your daily job look like ?

In general my job is quite varied, so somedays I spend the whole day in the office working in projects, but some other days I spend the day in my clients' companies, or travelling abroad to participate in project meetings.

What is your favorite work subject ?

What I most like about my work is the opportunity to learn continuously, participating in research projects and doing novel things that contribute to a sustainable development. On the other hand I also like to help companies to solve their problems, working closely with them to search solutions.

What excites you in the XERIC project?

The possibility to increase the energy efficiency of these systems by means of a new concept in the climate control systems. Related to my role in XERIC, I find it motivating to carry out a life cycle assessment of new systems and components not modeled to date.

You attended the 5th progress meeting in Monaco on 10 April. What will you remember the most from this meeting?

What I will remember the most from this meeting, but also from the rest of the project meetings, is the excellent work carried out up to now, and the willingness of all partners to solve the problems encountered throughout the project.

Are you participating in other international projects? Can you talk about them and explain the role you play?

At present I am coordinating the EE-METAL European funded project, a H2020 programme project. The main aim of EE-METAL project is to provide EU SMEs and industry with innovative technical, informational, commercial and financial tools in order for them to overcome the existing barriers that hinder the adoption of energy saving measures. The actions are targeted to Metalworking and Metal Articles SMEs, given that the MMA sector is one of the biggest manufacturing sectors in Europe and it is mostly composed by SMEs.

Thanks for answering my questions
Irene and all the best for your projects,
including XERIC !

Irene's skills

Engineering and technical services: integrated project management, technical assistance in industrial environment, environmental and energy projects and studies, industrial facilities, industrial safety

AIN, a partner in the XERIC project

The Asociación de la Industria Navarra is a private non-profit organization owned by its member companies (around 120) that finances itself by providing specialized services in different areas of knowledge and key specialties to the management and development of companies and organizations.

The Engineering business unit actively supports companies that comply with sustainable development guidelines and respect the environment, not only fulfilling legal requirements, but also applying the most adequate available technologies.

In the frame of XERIC, AIN is in charge of applying the Life Cycle Assessment approach to quantify the environmental impacts associated with the new and innovative Climate Control System, identifying areas to reduce these impacts and conduct to a more sustainable product. This study is also completed with a Life Cycle Cost Analysis.

XERIC in brief

XERIC is a European Research & Innovation Project

Start date: 1st June 2015

End date: 31st May 2018

Number of partners: 8

Coordinator:

Dr. Eng. S. GAETA

GVS spa

Italy

Programme:

H2020-GV-2014

Project Reference: 653605

Interview with **Clemens ALEXOWSKY**

PhD at the University of Duisburg-Essen
Germany

Clemens ALEXOWSKY

studied chemistry in Essen and did his master thesis at Evonik Industries studying additives for glass fiber reinforced polymers. Now he is a PhD student at the University of Duisburg-Essen in the working group for technical chemistry of Professor Matthias Ulbricht. As a part of the XERIC project his research is about preparation and characterization of membranes.

Can you please tell us a little bit about yourself through your career path ?

While studying chemistry, I got interested in polymer and membrane science, as it comprises abstract scientific content and links it with things from ordinary life. Also the wide field of applications in membrane science got me interested. It is common to do a PhD after studying chemistry and this working group and project suits my interests in the best way.

What is your PhD about, more precisely? What are you interested in?

My topic is directly linked to the membrane part of the XERIC project. Of course, for the project, the goal is to have the best membrane that could be produced. For the PhD it is also very important to investigate the possible processes and explain why certain membranes are achieved under certain circumstances.

Membrane science is really interesting, as you can find membranes for example in biology (cell tissue), water proof textiles and batteries. More specific, the preparation and characterization of membranes is a crossover of chemistry, physical chemistry and engineering. This makes it necessary to think outside the box and learn about new interesting things besides chemistry.

What excites you in the XERIC project ?

The project offers me to work for a very current topic, electric cars and comprises it

with the working field of membrane science. Also the input from different backgrounds (chemistry, engineering as well as industry, university) excites me. It is really interesting to see not only how something gets better with the input of science, but also how (in this case) a climate control system is built up from the basis with an alternative idea to reach the goal.

Each part of the project is ambitious itself. I think the biggest challenge is to combine all parts to one working unit, as the project will only be successful if every single part reaches its goal.

You attended the 5th progress meeting in Monaco on 10 April, followed by the 2nd workshop organized in the frame of the EVER forum in Monaco. What will you remember the most from this meeting ?

The project meeting in Monaco showed me that in a short time (less than two years) partners from different backgrounds grew together and work as a unit. The workshop underlined, in my point of view, the meaningfulness of interdisciplinary work. It is enriching to see how all the different fields of science use various techniques to work on the same problem.

What are your plans after your PhD ?

My contract ends in May 2018. Of course, I try to keep the time gap between the end of the contract and the defence as short as possible. My follow-up plan is, not so surprising, to find a job. I am quite open what it will be in detail.

Thanks for your time Clemens, and all the best for your projects !

UDE, a partner in the XERIC project

Universität Duisburg-Essen offers a broad spectrum of fields, with a strong focus on sciences, engineering and medicine.

The "Technische Chemie II" Chair (TCII) has a key position within research and teaching in UDE's Chemistry Department. Research carried out by Prof. Ulbricht's group is devoted to functional polymeric materials with a focus on separation membranes and particular emphasis on applications in water purification and related processes.

With advanced methods for membrane formation and characterization, the group makes essential contributions to reach XERIC's objectives. The work of UDE focuses on the development of advanced hydrophobic membranes to improve membrane contractor performance.

XERIC in brief

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